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The Rate of Fatal Accidents and Permanent Disability in the Italian Regions

It decreased by an average of 16.07% between 2018 and 2021

Istat calculates the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability. This value is calculated as the number of fatal accidents and those resulting in permanent disability out of the total employed (net of the armed forces) per 10,000. The data refers to the Italian regions in the period 2018-2021.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of fatal accidents and permanent disability in 2021.

Basilicata is in first place for the value of fatal accidents and permanent disability in 2021 with a value of 18.9 units, followed by the Marche with a value of 15, 2, and from Umbria with 15.1. In the middle of the table are Tuscany with a value of fatal accidents and permanent disability in 2021 equal to 12.4 units, followed by Sicily with a value equal to 12.3, and Emilia Romagna with a value of 11.4 units . Piedmont, Friuli Venezia Giulia and Lazio close the ranking with a value of 7.5 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in fatal accidents and permanent disability between 2018 and 2021.

Valle d'Aosta is in first place by value of the percentage change in fatal accidents and permanent disability with a value of -2.1 % corresponding to a variation from an amount of 9.7 units up to a value of 9.5 units equal to -0.2 units. Lombardy follows with a value equal to -2.6% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 7.8 units up to a value of 7.65 units equal to an amount of -0.2 units. In third place Puglia with a value equal to -5.3% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 13.3 units up to a value of 12.6 units equal to a reduction of -0.7 units. In the middle of the ranking there is Campania with a value equal to -10.2% corresponding to a variation from 10.8 units up to 9.7 units equal to an amount of -1.1 units. Liguria follows with a value equal to -15.3% equal to a variation from an amount of 15.00 units up to a value of 12.7 units equal to an amount of -2.3 units. Below is Umbria with a value equal to -16.1% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 18.00 units up to a value of 15.1 units equal to an amount of 2.9 units. At the bottom of the ranking is Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of -22.7% corresponding to a variation from 9.76 units up to 7.5 units equal to -2.2 units. Calabria follows with a variation equal to -23.8% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 18.1 units up to a value of 13.8 units equal to a reduction of -4.3 units. Sardinia closes the ranking with a value equal to -40.5% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 16.8 up to a value of 10.00 units equal to an amount of -6.8 units.

The value of the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability in the Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022.

The value of the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability decreased in Northern Italy from an amount of 10.2 units up to a value of 9.1 units corresponding to a variation of 1.10 units equal to -10.78%. The value of the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability decreased in the North-West from an amount of 8.5 units to a value of 8 units corresponding to a variation of -0.50 units equal to a value of -5.88 %. The value of the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability in the North-East decreased from an amount of 12.6 units to a value of 10.4 units equal to a value of -2.20 units corresponding to a variation of -17,46%. The value of the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability in the Center decreased from an amount of 12.4 units to 10.7 units corresponding

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to a variation of -1.70 units equal to -13.71%. The value of the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability in the South decreased from an amount of 14.4 units to a value of 12.00 units equal to an amount of -2.40 units corresponding to a variation of -16.67 %. The value of the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 14.00 units to a value of 12.1 units equal to an amount of -1.90 units corresponding to a variation of -13, 57%. The value of the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability in the Islands decreased from an amount of 15.3 units to a value of 11.6 units corresponding to a variation of -3.70 units equal to -24.18%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Lazio, Piedmont, Lombardy, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Valle d'Aosta, Campania, Veneto, Trentino Alto Adige;
- Cluster 2: Calabria, Abruzzo, Marche, Umbria, Sardinia, Tuscany, Liguria, Sicily, Basilicata, Molise, Emilia-Romagna, Puglia.

From the point of view of comparing the clusters we can see that the value of cluster 2-C2 is higher than the value of cluster 1-C1 or $C2 > C1$. We can note that the two clusters are quite heterogeneous from a geographical and per capita income point of view. However, there is certainly a greater weight of the southern regions in Cluster 2. Campania is the only southern region to participate in Cluster 1, characterized by a reduced value of the rate of accidents and permanent disability.

Conclusions. The rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability decreased significantly between 2018 and 2021 in the Italian regions. The southern regions were characterized by a significant reduction in the variable analyzed. The regions that experienced a significant reduction in the observed variable are Basilicata with -20.6%, Calabria with -23.8% and Sardinia with -40.5%. However, significant differences remain between the central-northern regions and the southern regions in terms of the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability. In the North-West, the value of the observed variable has the lowest value with an amount equal to 8. The corresponding values of the South, the South and the Islands are higher than those of the North-West by an amount corresponding to 51.25%, 50.00%, and 45.00%. The reduction in the rate of fatal accidents and permanent disability may be due to a significant change in the world of work increasingly oriented towards the service sector. The service sector is safer for workers than activities in the primary sector, such as agriculture and mining, and the secondary sector, such as manufacturing and construction. It is also very probable that an increased culture of legality has occurred which has reduced the intensity of manifestation of the observed variable.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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